

**TECHNIQUES FOR USING BUSINESS TOURISM TERMINOLOGY IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.**

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ABSTRACT

The lexical and semantic characteristics of certain terms linked to business travel in English and Uzbek are examined in this study. One of the most significant economic areas today is tourism. New terminology are evolving along with the advent of new forms of tourism. Terms for various fields were first brought into Uzbek in the previous century from Russian through European languages, although they are now exclusively borrowed terminology.

Keywords: Budget, term, type, tourism, industry, object, business, lexical-semantic.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqotda ingliz va o'zbek tillarida ish safari bilan bog'liq ayrim atamalarning leksik va semantik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Bugungi kunda eng muhim iqtisodiy yo'nalishlardan biri bu turizmdir. Turizmning yangi shakllari paydo bo'lishi bilan birga yangi terminologiya ham rivojlanmoqda. Turli sohalarga oid atamalar birinchi marta o'zbek tiliga o'tgan asrda rus tilidan yevropa tillari orqali olib kelingan, ammo hozirda ular faqat o'zlashtirilgan terminologiya hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Byudjet, termin, tur, turizm, soha, obyekt, biznes, leksik-semantik.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проанализированы лексико-семантические особенности ряда терминов, относящихся к деловому туризму, на английском и узбекском языках. Туризм-сегодня остается одним из важнейших направлений экономики страны. С появлением новых видов туризма появляются и новые термины. Если

в прошлом веке термины, относящиеся к различным отраслям, были заимствованы в узбекский язык из европейских языков через русский, то сегодня они заимствуются непосредственно из иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: Бюджет, термин, тур, туризм, сфера, объект, бизнес, лексико-семантический.

Nowadays, many things are being done to develop the country's economy. In particular, we are witnessing active changes in the field of tourism, which is one of the major links of economic development. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the decisions and decrees of the President in the field of tourism today are great steps taken to fill the gaps in this regard and bring tourism to the country level. As proof of our opinion, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the President of Uzbekistan's order of August 16, 2017 "The first plan for the development of the tourism sector in 2018-2019 The decision on the next measures" raised the work in the field of tourism to a new level.

Special attention is paid to tourism not only in today's country, but also in the time of the Timurid Empire. That is, the trips of the firstly tourists in Movarounnahr became active during the time of Amir Timur and his descendants.

The development of the tourism sector will definitely have a positive effect on the improvement of internal economic structures, as well as on the development of industries related to this sector. However, it is no secret that large financial resources are required to travel, to rest in a place other than the place of regularly habitation, to see new areas or to restore health in curative areas. These funds are used to get to the desired destination; stay overnight and for accommodation, meals and the use of various similar services is spent. It is expedient to partially use the state's social protection policy for the segments of the population in need of social protection. In developed countries, systems of organizing special trips for these population groups have been introduced, and through them, it is ensured that tourism services serve especially the disadvantaged segments of the population.

Tourism is legally carried out by tourist organizations. According to this, tourism is divided into several types: internal tourism, international tourism, amateur tourism, business tourism, ecotourism, sports tourism, auto tourism, tourism for expanding the level of knowledge, etc.¹

Business tourism is related to the tourist's professional activity, any organization, economy that brings income, aims at profit and does not violate the law; type of travel related to commercial, business activity.

Internal tourism is tourism organized by permanent residents of a country to other parts of the territory of that country. The term internal tourism has become a widely used lexical unit in recent years.

Social tourism is tourism in which travel costs are fully or partly covered by the state budget, extra-budgetary funds, and the employer.

Group (package) tourism is tourism consisting of an assemblage of several tourist services. This package includes services such as tour operator, flight, service, transfer, accommodation.

Service tourism is related to the professional and commercial interest of the tourist type of tourism. It includes personal service trips and holding various events.

Individual tourism - tourism consisting of a set of services, including accommodation, meals, transfers, excursions and entertainment programs based approximately one or several tourists.

Recreational tourism. According to the purpose of the organize, it is organized travel for leisure as opposed to service tourism.

Ecotourism refers to ecotourism objects (unique places of nature that give esthetic pleasure, healing natural habitats, natural and anthropogenic restructures, physical and natural phenomena, objects of historical and cultural estate, ethnic lifestyle of the local people, etc.) is organized popular tourism aimed at ensuring physical development.²

¹ Rita Temmerman "The translation of domain-specific languages and multilingual terminology management". 2005. P:46.

² [Виноградова Л.В. Терминология туризма английского и русского языков в синхронном и диахронном аспектах.](#) - Великий Новгород, 2011. – 23 с.10.02.19. стр: 12

New terms are appearing in connection with the appearance of new types of tourism. Let us talk about business tourism among these terms. In the commonly used explanatory dictionary of the current Uzbek language, business (English. business - work, activity) is any organizational, economic activity that brings income and aims to gain profit; commerce; the meanings of business are given. Tourism (French. tourisme < tour - take a walk (travel)).

1. Trip organized for the purpose of both seeing the world, gaining knowledge, learning, and relaxing. Taking into account that tourism is developing more and more, the vehicle of tourist trains has been increased. "Science and life"

2. Sport. Group trips organized for the purpose of physical training for the organism.

When we looked at the Oxford dictionary of English, we saw that the word business was given a wider definition than in the Uzbek language:

1. Pul evaziga tovarlar yoki xizmatlar ishlab chiqarish, sotib olish, sotish yoki etkazib berish faoliyati. (The activity of making, selling, buying, supplying goods or services for money);

2. Kasbingizning bir qismi bo'lgan ish. (Work that is part of your job);

3. Kompaniya tomonidan bajarilgan ish hajmi va boshqalar; shu ishning tezligi yoki sifati. (The amount of work done by a company, etc; the rate or quality of this work.);

4. Muayyan shaxs yoki tashkilotga tegishli bo'lgan narsa. (Something that concerns a particular person or organization);

5. Muhokama qilinishi yoki bajarilishi kerak bo'lgan masalalar. (Things that need to be discussed or done);

6. Vaziyat yoki faoliyatga nisbatan o'z nuqtai nazariningiz yoki munosabatingiz borligi (A situation or activity, especially one that you have a particular opinion about or attitude towards).

As we divided tourism into several groups above, business tourism is also divided into several types: individual travels, group travels, events (meetings, incentives, conferences, exhibitions (MICE), team building and exchange of places on study trips.

Business tourism works with many business corporations: hotel network, professionally combined trade fairs in many countries and exhibitions, business centers founders in many countries.³ Of course, each sector has its own terms. In this article, we consider the lexical semantic features of a number of terms related to business tourism in English and Uzbek languages.

As we all know, tourism in Uzbekistan is one of the sectors that is rapidly developing and makes a significant contribution to the country's economy. Each field has its own terminology. Also, the terminology of tourism obtain a large place in the Uzbek terminological system. Its development is distinguished by linguistic and extralinguistic factors. In the last century, the terms related to various fields were adopted into the Uzbek language from European languages through the Russian language, and these days they are directly internalized from foreign languages and as an example, we will consider the lexical semantic meanings of words related to business tourism in the Uzbek language.

Each type of tourism has its own terms. Also business tourism too. We face them from the moment we set off on a travel. Subsequent processes also have their own terms. As can be seen from the above results, the terminology of tourism in Uzbek language is at the initial stage of formation, and because of the development of the field, its composition is enriched with new special units. Since tourism first emerged because of economic activity in England, this area is recognized as its homeland. In addition, if we take into account that the English language is in the leading position in the terminology of international tourism, it is natural that most of the borrowed terms in the Uzbek language were borrowed from this language. When we compared two languages, namely Uzbek and English, regarding the terminologies of the same field - tourism, we witnessed that some terms are used in Uzbek as their own, and some alternative versions are used. Many terms in English are given in English. Nevertheless, even in this language we can find words taken from other languages.

³ Sudhanshu Yoshi. Sustainable Tourism Supply Chain Management. Release scheduled for October 1, 2022. P: 16.

In conclusion, we can say that creating explanatory, electronic and translation dictionaries of existing tourism terms in the Uzbek language is one of the important tasks of Uzbek terminology. Giving and explaining terms in explanatory dictionaries and special dictionaries for touristic terms serves to familiarize the student with the most necessary and general concepts of this subject and to increase his level of knowledge, as well as to create interest in this field.

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